

Title: Hydrocarbons for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

Hydrocarbons, which are made up of only carbon and hydrogen, are the building blocks of organic chemistry. In today's industries, they are the main sources of fuels, intermediates, and polymers. This paper methodically examines the taxonomy, nomenclature, physical and chemical properties, reaction mechanisms, and industrial relevance of hydrocarbons. The paper talks on alkanes, alkenes, alkynes, and arenes, focusing on their typical reactions such substitution, addition, oxidation, and polymerization, as well as specific effects like Markovnikov and Anti-Markovnikov addition. Mind mapping helps chemistry students understand and remember concepts better by visually organizing the complicated web of ideas. It also helps them think more analytically.

Key Words

Hydrocarbons, Alkanes, Alkenes, Alkynes, Arenes, Polymerization, Markovnikov rule, Mind mapping

HYDROCARBONS

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